

**Training manual for RoB 2
risk of bias assessment in COVID-19 trials
eligible for the COVID-19
living network meta-analysis**

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OVERVIEW

On March 11th 2020 the World Health Organization declared the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) a global pandemic. COVID-19 has caused significant morbidity and mortality in many countries and has also had dramatic effects on the global economy.

In order to face the current crisis, there is an urgent need for effective interventions for preventing and treating COVID-19 and countries around the world are scaling up national initiatives to accelerate the development of new drugs and vaccines. A considerable number of randomised clinical trials evaluating the effectiveness of interventions for preventing and treating COVID-19 are expected to be completed in the next months and years.

Decision-makers, researchers, and clinicians need access to a systematic and high-quality synthesis of data from all these trials. This is why a team of international researchers, led by Professors Boutron and Ravaud from the French Cochrane Centre, decided to conduct a **living network meta-analysis**¹ to synthesize and critically appraise in real-time the available trial-based evidence.

An important step in this process is the **assessment of the risk of bias** in the trial results. The risk of bias will be assessed using the revised Cochrane tool to assess risk of bias in randomised trials, RoB 2.^{2,3}

In this manual we provide a **training kit for RoB 2 adapted for COVID-19 trials**. It is intended for a person preparing for the risk of bias assessment of a COVID-19 trial eligible for the network meta-analysis. The manual consists of:

- an overview of challenges of conducting risk of bias assessment in COVID-19 trials;
- a focused guidance of applying the RoB 2 tool to COVID-19 trials;
- a list of key Cochrane resources on RoB 2.

Your feedback is important!

This manual will be revised based on the feedback we will receive. If you have any comments on the training materials, please email Camilla Hansen (coordinator of the Cochrane Bias Methods Group) at Camilla.Hansen3@rsyd.dk.

¹ <https://covid-nma.com/the-project/>

² Higgins JPT, Savović J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Sterne JAC. Chapter 8: Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial. In: Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA (editors). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 6.0 (updated July 2019). Cochrane, 2019. Available from www.training.cochrane.org/handbook.

³ Sterne JAC, Savović J, Page MJ, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials *BMJ* 2019; 366 :l4898.

PART 1. CHALLENGES OF CONDUCTING RISK OF BIAS ASSESSMENT IN COVID-19 TRIALS

Bias, imprecision, and external validity

Bias is a systematic error, or deviation from the truth, in results.⁴ Conducting risk of bias assessment allows to assess study design features (related to internal validity) that can lead to overestimation or underestimation of the true effect of an intervention. This process is fundamental when conducting evidence synthesis because if biased trial results are included in a meta-analysis it may provide a precise, and therefore influential, but biased result.

It is important to remember that:

1. Bias is a systematic error and should not be confused with **imprecision** which refers to random errors. Precision refers to how close multiple estimates of the same outcome are to each other, and not to how close they are to the true value. Precision in a trial is often closely related to the number of included patients, or number of observed events, and addressed in the statistical analysis.
2. Bias deals with internal validity (i.e., are the results really true within the included sample?) and should not be confused with **external validity** which refers instead to the generalizability of the results of a study across populations and settings. Although this is a very important aspect in any trial, it is not addressed in RoB 2.

The logistics of trials conducted during a pandemic

It is important to be aware of the **challenges** of conducting clinical trials during the intense crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Trialists are under pressure to identify effective treatments in the shortest time possible and in a situation with increased demands on the healthcare services. Also, insufficient knowledge on both the virus and the associated disease (e.g., immune response, disease progression) is a challenge, and so are the quarantines and travel limitations with some trials having follow-up visits conducted via phone and not in-person.

Another important problem is recruitment of participants. For example, a Chinese trial of hydroxychloroquine was terminated early because ‘the recruitment of eligible patients was unexpectedly difficult’.⁵ This happened because of the many COVID-19 trials launched at the same time and the rapid decline in eligible new cases in China in March 2020.

In the interest of expediting dissemination of information, research results are also being published at an unprecedented pace. It usually takes several months to go from submission to publication in peer-reviewed journals. During the COVID-19 pandemic this time has been

⁴Sterne JAC, Savović J, Page MJ, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials *BMJ* 2019; 366 :l4898.

⁵Tang W, Cao Z, Han M. Hydroxychloroquine in patients with COVID-19: an open-label, randomized, controlled trial. 2020. MedRxiv preprint doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.10.20060558>

shortened to even less than one week in some cases. Trial results are also published on pre-prints repositories before peer-review. Rapid information sharing during a pandemic is clearly important but risks compromising scientific scrutiny.

It is also worth mentioning that newly developed drugs or vaccines for COVID-19 represent an opportunity for pharmaceutical companies.⁶ This issue will be addressed below in a dedicated section of this manual.

The living network meta-analysis identifies randomised trials with three different purposes: trials of interventions for treating COVID-19, trials of non-vaccine interventions to prevent COVID-19, and trials of COVID-19 vaccines. This training manual is intended to be used for all trial purposes, and guidance is relevant for all trials unless otherwise stated.

Risk of bias at the trial level, outcome level, and result level

One of the key features of RoB 2 is that it requires a **result-focussed assessment** of risk of bias and not an assessment for the trial as a whole. This happens because of two important reasons:

1. **Different outcomes in a trial can be at different levels of risk bias.** For example, a patient reported outcome tends to be at high risk of bias due to the lack of blinding of the outcome assessor while more objective outcomes like all cause-mortality are not at high risk.
2. **There can be result level differences.** By result we mean a measurement of the outcome at a specific time and analysed in specific way. For example, when a trial reports a result that is both unadjusted and adjusted for several covariates, depending on which of the two results you are looking at, you could have a different risk of bias assessment.

In order to conduct the risk of bias assessment, you will need to check the outcomes listed in the protocol of the COVID-19 living network meta-analysis⁷ and then conduct an assessment for all trial's results that are related to those outcomes.

Do not assess risk of bias at the trial level.

Focus your assessment on a specific result of an outcome in a trial.

Do not assess risk of bias of all the trial's results, but only of the ones listed in the protocol of the living network meta-analysis.

⁶Lundh A, Lexchin J, Mintzes B, Schroll JB, Bero L. Industry sponsorship and research outcome. The Cochrane database of systematic reviews. 2017;2:Mr000033.

⁷Boutron I, Chaimni A, Devane D, et al. Interventions for preventing and treating COVID-19: protocol for a living mapping of research and a living systematic review. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3820266#.Xs432Mj7Q2w>

Retrieving multiple information sources

Before starting the RoB 2 assessment it is important to realize that the assessment is not of a trial publication, but of the **totality of information on the trial and its results**. The types of sources for this assessment could be:

- main study report (published paper and available pre-print versions. If both are available, both will be used, including any appendices/supplementary files), and updated reports when available;
- protocol;
- statistical analysis plan;
- trial registration;
- information provided by the authors or the sponsor;
- company-owned clinical study reports.

The project leaders will provide you with all the available materials on the trial that has been assigned to you. Trial authors will also be contacted in case protocols are not publicly available. This will be done centrally by the project leaders and you will not be required to liaise with the authors. If the authors provide additional information, you will be asked to revise the risk of bias assessment accordingly.

Do not base your risk of bias assessment only on the final study report.
Assess the totality of information on the trial.

Discordant information

It is possible that you will find discordant information between the different sources mentioned above (e.g., the trial registry and the final study report). The presence of conflicting information represents a **red flag** and the trial will be considered as high risk for the specific risk of bias domain you are assessing. In addition, you should report the presence of discordant information to the project leaders who will then contact the trial authors.

PART 2. HOW TO APPLY THE ROB 2 DOMAINS TO COVID-19 TRIALS

The assessment of risk of bias of the chosen trial result(s) involves five distinct domains. Within each domain, RoB 2 assessors answer one or more signalling questions, with answers leading to judgments of: **low risk of bias**, **some concerns**, or **high risk of bias**.

In this section of the manual, for each RoB 2 domain you will find:

- A brief description of what the domain focuses on
- The main issues you need to consider and guidance on how to assess them
- Specific guidance for the assessment of COVID-19 trials
- A list of ‘Do’s and Don’ts’

We recommend that before reading this section you familiarise yourself with the Cochrane resources on RoB 2 that are listed in part 3 of the manual as they provide an in-depth analysis of each risk of bias domain.

Domain 1: Bias arising from the randomisation process

The rationale for randomisation is to **minimise allocation bias**, i.e., uneven distribution of prognostic factors between the compared groups. Failure to properly implement randomisation could result in unbalanced distribution of patients with bad prognosis between groups.

Issues you need to consider:

1. Whether the allocation sequence was random
2. Whether the allocation sequence was adequately concealed
3. Whether baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomisation process

Issue 1 and 2: allocation sequence generation and concealment

Randomisation is a two-step process. The first one is the **generation of an unbiased allocation sequence**. A computer-generated list is usually considered an appropriate method to do this. Alternation or assignment based on dates or patient record number are instead considered inadequate. The second step is the **concealment of the allocation sequence**. Examples of appropriate methods are: central randomisation by a third party (e.g. a pharmacy) or use of sequentially numbered sealed opaque envelopes.

Failure to implement one of the two processes described above increases the risk that the allocation of patients into groups is influenced by prognostic factors.

Issue 2: baseline differences

In order to assess **baseline differences**, you will need to check Table 1 that usually contains the characteristics of participants and assess whether baseline imbalances in probable predictive factors of health outcomes suggest a problem with randomisation. A substantial excess in

statistically significant differences in baseline characteristics could be an indicator that randomisation was not performed adequately. By chance, we normally expect that 1 in 20 characteristics should differ at the conventional $p < 0.05$ threshold. If you find an excess of these differences, it could be a sign that there was a problem with randomisation. Check also if the differences always go in the same direction (e.g., favouring the intervention group). Please consider that small trials are more prone to baseline imbalances than larger trials. Baseline imbalances in small trials (<300 patients) will therefore be disregarded.

When assessing baseline differences in **COVID-19 trials**, pay attention to the **predictive factors of health outcomes** listed in Table 1. Imbalances suggest a problem if they systematically favour one arm over the other (e.g., younger participants, fewer patients with severe or critical condition).

Table 1. Predictive factors of health outcomes in COVID-19 trials

<p>Predictive factors (Please note that the list of predictive factors may evolve over time due to new knowledge)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Ethnicity/socioeconomic status • Comorbidities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ diabetes ○ chronic respiratory diseases ○ hypertension ○ obesity ○ immunosuppressed/organ transplant • Invasive/non-invasive ventilation in Intensive Care Units (ICU) • Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) • PaO₂ /FiO₂ (ratio of arterial oxygen partial pressure (PaO₂) to fractional inspired oxygen (FiO₂)) • COVID-19 severity (i.e., mild, moderate, severe and critical disease). As described in the protocol of the living network meta-analysis, this is how we will define disease severity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ mild disease: clinical symptoms are mild with no sign of pneumonia on imaging ○ moderate disease: fever and respiratory symptoms with radiological findings of pneumonia and requiring oxygen (3 L/min > oxygen 5 L/min) ○ severe: cases meeting any of the following criteria: - respiratory distress (≥ 30 breaths/min), - oxygen saturation $\leq 93\%$ at rest in ambient air or oxygen saturation $\leq 97\%$ with O₂ > 5 L/min, - PaO₂/FiO₂ ≤ 300 mmHg (1 mmHg=0.133 kPa). PaO₂/FiO₂ in high-altitude areas (> 1,000 m above sea level) will be corrected by the following formula: PaO₂/FiO₂ x [atmospheric pressure (mmHg)/760], - chest imaging showing obvious lesion progression within 24-48 hr ○ critical disease: cases meeting any of the following criteria: - respiratory failure and requiring mechani-
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	cal ventilation, - shock, -other organ failure that requires ICU care
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Do not confuse allocation concealment (up to the point of assignment of the intervention) with blinding of participants and outcome assessors which aims to prevent bias after randomisation and will be assessed in the following domain.

If the description of the allocation concealment is very vague (e.g., there is no information regarding sealing or opacity of the envelopes), answer No information to question 1.2 and do not automatically assume that it is high risk.

Take into account the predictive factors mentioned above when assessing baseline differences in COVID-19 trials.

Do not assess the study as high risk if you find baseline imbalances in small trials (<300 patients).

In large trials (>300 patients), do not assess the study as high risk if you find only a small number of statistically significant differences in baseline characteristics (1/20).

Check whether the differences in baseline characteristics always go in the same direction (e.g., favouring the intervention group).

Domain 2: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions

By intended interventions we mean the interventions that are consistent with the intentions of the investigators and that have been specified in the trial protocol. Failure to implement what was described in the protocol, administration of additional treatments not consistent with the protocol, or lack of adherence by the trial's participants represent deviations from intended intervention.

The assessment for this domain differs according to whether you are trying to quantify the effect of assignment to the interventions at baseline regardless of the interventions they actually received during follow-up, or the effect of starting and adhering to intervention. You will be asked to assess this domain for the **effect of assignment to intervention**.

According to RoB 2, the only deviations from intended intervention that are addressed (in relation to the effect of assignment to intervention), are those that: a) arise because of the trial context, b) are inconsistent with the trial protocol, and c) influence the outcome. However, we recognise that it can be difficult to clearly identify what are the intended intervention, the trial context, and the standard clinical practice in the fluctuating environment of a global pandemic. Moreover, RoB 2 has been developed for a traditional systematic review directly comparing two interventions, while we are currently using it in the much broader context of a network meta-analysis. Therefore, for the purpose of the current project, we decided to adopt a pragmatic approach to the question on deviation from the intended intervention.

When assessing this risk of bias domain, these are the issues you need to consider:

1. Whether participants were aware of the assigned intervention
2. Whether carers and trial personnel were aware of participants' assigned intervention
3. Whether deviations from the intended intervention arose because of the trial context (beyond what you would expect in usual practice); and, if so, whether these deviations were balanced between groups and likely to have affected the outcome
4. Whether an appropriate analysis was used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention. If no appropriate analysis was used, consider whether there was potential for a substantial impact on the result.

Issue 1 and 2: awareness of assigned intervention

As a first step you will be asked to assess whether participants, carers, and trial personnel were aware/unaware of intervention groups during the trial. This is an important issue because in unblinded trials the patients assigned to the comparator group could seek the experimental intervention or other interventions (i.e., co-interventions). Similarly, if the carers or trial personnel are aware of the assigned intervention, its implementation could differ between the groups.

Some of the **COVID-19 trials** identified so far are **not blinded**. Lack of blinding may cause bias if it leads to deviations from the intended intervention that differ between the intervention groups. However, lack of blinding does not in itself lead to high risk of bias (e.g. in COVID-19 trials that assess patients admitted to an intensive care unit, knowledge of intervention assignment is not an issue for patients due to their critical conditions).

Issue 3: deviations because of trial context

According to RoB 2 **even open trials can be at low risk of bias** if there were no deviations from intended intervention that arose because of the trial context. In order to assess whether there were deviations from the intended intervention, you will need to check the flow chart and results section for indications of intervention non-receipt and cross-over. (i.e., patients in one treatment arm receiving the intervention of the other arm that they were not assigned to). Deviations occurring in a small number of patients, and deviations that were not attributable to the experimental context, but might occur in usual clinical settings, will not be considered to indicate high risk of bias.

Another important issue to consider while assessing this domain is the presence of **co-interventions** administered post-randomisation and whether they are administered similarly in both arms of the trial. In the present COVID-19 context it is reasonable to expect that patients are treated with different types of interventions. If co-interventions are not reported, this raises concerns about risk of bias. Overall, we consider deviations due to the trial context to be cross-over and an imbalance in the administration of co-interventions of interest between arms.

You will also need to search for the number of participants that received co-interventions in each arm. In the present COVID-19 pandemic, patients in clinical settings might be treated with different types of interventions. These treatments might change over time while new

evidence emerges about COVID-19 and its treatment. Through the expert knowledge of members of the review group, we have identified a list of three main **co-intervention categories for trials investigating treatment of COVID-19**:

- antivirals;⁸
- immunotherapies (e.g., Monoclonal antibodies);
- corticosteroids (e.g., Dexamethasone).

If the number of participants that received these treatments is not clear, you will consider the response to signalling question 2.3. ('Were there deviations from the intended intervention arose because of the trial context?') to be No Information and this risk of bias domain will be assessed as some concern.

If the number of participants that received these treatments is reported, you will need to compare the number of participants that received each co-intervention category between the two arms. If they are balanced, the assessment will be low risk. If they are not similar, we recommend that you discuss the difference between arms while factoring in the sample size to determine the likeliness of its effect on the outcome.

For trials investigating **prevention of COVID-19 or vaccines**, we consider personal protective measures such as social distancing and wearing masks as potential co-interventions. However, these co-interventions are often not reported or measured and the assessment should be 'low risk' unless there is evidence that the number of participants receiving these co-interventions is not similar between the two arms.

Issue 4: appropriateness of analysis method

Finally, when you assess whether the analysis approach was appropriate to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention, remember that in general, intention-to-treat analyses (ITT) where participants are analysed in the same group to which they were randomised will be considered appropriate. Trialists may also use a 'modified intention-to-treat' analysis in which participants with missing outcome data are excluded. This analysis will be considered appropriate for the purpose of this domain because the problem of missing outcome data will be addressed in a separate RoB 2 domain. However, it will be considered inappropriate if patients are excluded from the analysis for any other reasons than missing data. Instead naïve 'per-protocol' analyses and 'as treated' analyses where participants are analysed in the group of the treatment that they actually received will be considered inappropriate, for example when contamination (cross over) occur.

For **primary/critical outcomes** (i.e. binary outcomes) data for missing patients are imputed. Patients that were excluded because they did not receive the assigned intervention are imputed 'no event' and patients that were excluded because they died or had an event are imputed 'event' in the analysis where appropriate. If such an imputation is possible, it follows the principles of an ITT analysis and is thereby considered appropriate regardless of the trial authors' analysis. For **secondary/important outcomes** (i.e. time-to-event outcomes), we rely

⁸Please consider any antiviral. However, if the authors report only remdesivir, you will consider information from remdesivir enough to assess this co-intervention.

on the trial authors' analysis. Therefore, you should take into account the reasons for excluding patients from the analysis and consider the analysis method inappropriate if the number of excluded patients is important or imbalanced.

For trials investigating **COVID-19 vaccines**, analyses are often conducted as per-protocol analyses. Data are not imputed in vaccine trials due to the very large sample sizes. In your assessment, please pay careful consideration to the reasons for excluding patients. Patients excluded from the analysis because they received no dose or only one of two doses are considered in domain 2, whereas patients with missing data are considered in domain 3.

The assessment of this domain is to be performed separately at the outcome level. The risk of bias assessment should be done separately for each clinically important outcome that is included in a meta-analysis.

 DON'TS	<p>Changes to intervention that have been described in the trial protocol should not be considered as deviations from intended intervention.</p> <p>Do not assess all unblinded trial as high risk of bias by default.</p> <p>Pay attention to the co-interventions administered post-randomisation and whether they are administered similarly in both arms of the trial.</p>	
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Domain 3: Bias due to missing outcome data

Missing outcome data, for example due to participants' withdrawals or loss to follow-up, can lead to bias in the observed effect estimate. This domain addresses also biases introduced by procedures used to account for the missing outcome data.

Issues you need to consider:

1. Whether data for the outcome were available for all, or nearly all, participants randomised
2. Whether there is evidence that the result was not biased by missing outcome data
3. Whether the proportions of missing outcome data differ between intervention groups
4. Whether missingness in the outcome could depend on its true value (for example when participants in the experimental group drop out because of side effects from the drug; see further explanation in the text below) and whether this was likely

There is not a universal threshold to decide how much is too much missing outcome data. Traditionally, less than 5% missing outcome data is considered as small.

Even if data are not available for all participants, risk of bias could still be low if sensitivity analyses confirm that plausible values of the missing outcome data could have no significant impact on the estimated effect of the intervention.

Another issue to consider is whether the proportions of missing outcome data differ between intervention groups; in this regard a red flag would be a trial with a 20% drop out in the experimental group and a 2% drop out in the control group.

Apart from examining differences in the proportion of missing outcome data between intervention groups, it is important also to consider the **reasons that outcome data are missing**. Missing outcome data will lead to bias if the missingness is related to the true value of the outcome. In this regard, it is important to examine whether the trialists describe the reasons why participants have missing data. If the missing data are related to the failure of the measuring instrument, the risk of bias will be low as this is not related to the outcome. Instead, if missing data are related to participants' withdrawal because of their health status (e.g., adverse effects of the pharmacologic intervention or lack of efficacy) then it is possible that the missingness in the outcome was influenced by its true value. Pay also attention at whether the reasons for missing outcome data differ between the intervention groups as this is the situation most likely leading to bias.

These are multiple possible reasons for missing outcome data:

- Consent withdrawals
- Participants stopped the treatment because of toxic side effects
- Participants died
- Participants did not attend a study visit or attended a study visit but did not provide relevant data
- Data lost or unavailable
- Premature ending of the trial

Instead, if participants for whom outcome data are available, are excluded by the investigators for other reasons (e.g., a naïve 'per protocol' analysis restricted to participants who received the intended intervention) this will be addressed in the previous domain 'Bias due to deviations from intended interventions'.

Finally, it is important to mention that there could be differences between how missing data is handled at the study level versus at the review/meta-analysis level. For example, even if the trial excluded patients who died from the analysis, we plan to include these patients at the meta-analysis level. This means that although the risk of bias assessment for the domain 'Bias due to missing outcome data' would be high at the trial level, when the trial is considered within the meta-analysis, it will be considered low risk for exclusions due to deaths of participants.

When assessing **COVID-19 trials**, we recommend to consider that if you are assessing the outcome of a **pharmacologic intervention**, **>5%** of participants randomised missing from the analysis poses risk of bias. This cutoff applies for both binary and continuous outcomes. The exception is all-cause mortality in a trial population of mild severity, which is considered as a rare binary outcome, therefore **<5%** of missing data poses concerns for risk of bias. Instead, if you are assessing the outcome of a **non-pharmacologic intervention** - where the outcome is not binary and a rare event - we consider that **>10%** of participants randomised missing from the analysis poses a risk of bias.

Some participants may be deliberately excluded because the trialists chose a 'per protocol' analysis. Biases introduced by such analyses are addressed in the domain on 'deviations from intended interventions' and not in this domain.

Use the cut-offs suggested above to assess the missing outcome data in pharmacologic and non-pharmacologic interventions.

Domain 4: Bias in measurement of the outcome

Errors in the measurement or classification of an outcome can bias the estimates of the effect of an intervention. In general, errors in the measurement of the outcome are less likely when the outcome assessors are blinded. Please remember that this is a domain where it is important to consider that the assessment may differ depending on the outcome you are considering because some outcomes are more prone to bias compared to others.

Issues you need to consider:

1. Whether the method of measuring the outcome was inappropriate
2. Whether measurement or ascertainment of the outcome could have differed between intervention groups
3. Whether outcome assessors were aware of the intervention received by study participants
4. Whether assessment of the outcome could have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received

It is important that outcomes in randomised trials are assessed using appropriate methods, for example using a measurement instrument that has been demonstrated to have good validity. As a general rule, it is unlikely that pre-specified outcomes in trials are measured using inappropriate methods. We acknowledge that for safety outcomes, this may be likely, however, unless there is clear evidence to the contrary, we assess that outcomes were measured in the same manner.

This domain also looks at whether there were systematic differences between the intervention groups in how outcomes were assessed. Outcomes should be measured using a method that is comparable across intervention groups (e.g., same methods, same thresholds, same time points).

The following issue to consider is **blinding**. There are three possible outcome assessors in a trial:

- The participant if the trial measures a patient-reported outcome (e.g., pain, nausea)
- The intervention provider
- An external outcome assessor (e.g., a technician performing an automated test in the laboratory)

Errors in the measurement of the outcome are less likely when the outcome assessors are blinded. In unblinded trials, you will need to judge whether it is likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received. Your assessment will need to take into account the **type of outcome** and the **degree of judgement** involved in assessing that outcome. For example, for patient-reported outcomes, the outcome assessment can be influenced by knowledge of intervention received and this could lead to a judgement of some concerns or high risk of bias depending on the type of outcome.

Some of the **COVID-19 trials** identified so far are **not blinded**. In the following Table you will find a list of rules that will help you to judge whether the measurement of each outcome in unblinded COVID-19 trials could have been affected by knowledge of the intervention assignment.

Table 2. Classification of study outcomes and its implications for risk of bias in unblinded studies

Outcome type	Review outcome	Outcome assessor	Implications for ROB if the assessor is aware of the intervention assignment
Observer-reported outcome not involving judgement	All-cause mortality	The observer	The assessment is not likely to be influenced by knowledge of the intervention assignment
	Viral negative conversion		
	Time to viral negative conversion		
Outcomes that reflect decisions made by the intervention provider	Time to clinical improvement	The care provider	<p>Although the assessment could <i>possibly</i> be influenced by knowledge of the intervention assignment (signaling question 4.4), we did <i>not</i> consider this <i>likely</i> to have happened in the context of a pandemic (signaling question 4.5).</p> <p>For the outcome incidence of clinical improvement and time to clinical improvement: our assessment depended on the definition used for clinical improvement or recovery. We applied the process described above if the definition was based on the WHO score.</p> <p>For the outcome incidence of score 7 or above (intubation or death): We consider that the assessment cannot possibly be influenced by knowledge of the intervention as-</p>
	Clinical improvement		
	Score 7 or above in the WHO clinical progression scale		

			signment (signaling question 4.4).
Observer-reported outcome involving some judgment	No outcome considered	The observer	The assessment could be influenced by knowledge of the intervention assignment
Other composite outcomes	Adverse events	Depending on how the event was ascertained: the observer or the patient	If the outcome includes only observer-reported events not involving judgement (e.g., laboratory measures) we consider that it cannot be influenced by knowledge of the intervention assignment.
	Serious adverse events		If the outcome includes patient-reported or observer-reported events involving judgement (e.g., clinician-assessed health events), we consider it can be influenced by knowledge of the intervention assignment (signalling question 4.4), but is not likely to (signalling question 4.5), leading to an assessment of some concern.

Do not assess unblinded trials as high risk by default. Your assessment will need to take into account the type of outcome and the degree of judgement involved in assessing that outcome.

Consider also whether there were systematic differences between the intervention groups in how outcomes were assessed.

Domain 5: Bias in selection of the reported result

A trial result can be biased because it has been selected based on its direction, magnitude or statistical significance; from multiple outcome measurements (e.g., multiple scales, multiple time points); or multiple analyses (e.g., unadjusted versus adjusted models).

It is important to remember that RoB 2 deals only with **risk of bias in available study results** and does not address selective non-reporting of results (either because of non-publication of whole studies or selective reporting of outcomes). For example, if mortality is measured (according to the protocol), but the final report of the trial contains no data on mortality, such non-reporting will cause bias in a meta-analysis of results for mortality. Selective

non-reporting of outcome domains will be separately assessed at the meta-analysis level (see the following section of the manual).

Issues you need to consider:

1. Whether the trial was analysed in accordance with a prespecified plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis
2. Whether the numerical result being assessed is likely to have been selected, on the basis of the results, from multiple eligible outcome measurements within the outcome domain
3. Whether the numerical result being assessed is likely to have been selected, on the basis of the results, from multiple eligible analyses of the data

The best way to know whether results are selectively reported is to look at **the trial registry, trial protocol, and the pre-specified analysis plan**. Contact with the trialists might also be needed to clarify the reason for discrepancies identified between the protocol and the final publication.

In order to answer the questions on ‘multiple outcome measurements’ and ‘multiple analyses of the data’, you will need to examine the trial registry, the protocol, and the statistical analysis plan and compare the pre-specified outcomes to the outcomes reported in the final paper/pre-print. This assessment will be done only for the trial’s outcomes that are included in the living network meta-analysis.

Protocols and pre-specified analysis plan are sometimes **not publicly available** for COVID-19 trials and this leads to several trials being initially rated as some concerns for this domain. These documents will be requested from the corresponding authors in order to re-assess this domain. However, if one of the three documents (i.e. the trial registry, protocol, or statistical analysis plan) is available and the outcomes reported in the final publication had been clearly described in any of those documents, you can still assess this domain as low risk even if the remaining documents are not available. This requires that the available document contains information on type of outcome and time point of the measurement. In order to assist you in the assessment of this domain, please consider the following guidance:

1. For dichotomous outcomes (e.g. all-cause mortality at day 7), you will assess this domain as low risk if the outcome and the time frame reported in the registry, protocol, or statistical analysis plan and in the final publication are consistent (e.g. all-cause mortality at day 7 reported both in the registry and final publication); even if you do not have access to details on the methods planned to conduct the analysis (e.g. statistical models or adjustment procedures).
2. For time-to-event outcomes (e.g. time to clinical improvement), you will assess the domain as:
 - a. Some concern if there is no clear description of the analysis plan for the outcome in any of the three sources (i.e. protocol, statistical analysis plan, or registry)
 - b. Low risk if the outcome is reported as time-to-event with time frame in the registry, protocol, or statistical analysis plan and the outcome presented in the

final publication is specified as a time-to-event variable in the methods or reported as hazard ratio (HR) in the results; even if you do not have access to details in terms of the methods planned to do the analysis (e.g. statistical models or adjustment procedures).

Exceptionally, for mortality outcomes, we consider it low risk of bias if the number of deaths at the end of the trial follow-up is reported, even if this is not pre-specified (as mortality should always be reported). Furthermore, for survival analyses, we do not consider unclear time zero or changing time zero from randomisation to after start of the treatment (e.g. from day zero to day three) to be inappropriate. Finally, for adjusted analyses we consider adjustment appropriate, even if it is unclear whether the covariates were pre-specified.

DO'S

DON'TS

Do not consider selective non-reporting of outcome domains under this risk of bias domain.

Some differences between the analysis plan and the final publication could be due to justified changes to the protocol (e.g., a pre-specified subgroup analysis need to be modified because the distribution of data differed from what trialists anticipated).

Overall risk of bias

The judgements for all the previous domains provide the basis for an overall risk of bias judgement for the specific trial result that you are assessing. In RoB 2, the overall risk of bias corresponds to either the worst risk of bias judgement in any of the domains or there are some concerns for multiple domains (see Table 3).

Table 3. RoB2 overall risk of bias

Low risk of bias	The study is judged to be at low risk of bias for all domains for this result
Some concerns	The study is judged to be at some concerns in at least one domain for this result
High risk of bias	<p>The study is judged to be at high risk of bias in at least one domain for this result</p> <p>OR</p> <p>The study is judged to have some concerns for multiple domains in a way that substantially lowers confidence in the result</p>

We cannot provide a universal rule to assess overall risk of bias of COVID-19 trials. In general, please consider that if two domains are assessed as some concerns but your judgement was leaning towards high risk of bias for those domains, it would be reasonable to consider the trial as high risk overall for that specific result. Conversely if two domains are assessed as some concerns but they were close to be at low risk of bias, the trial will not be considered as high risk for this specific result.

Try to look back at the trial as a whole (for the specific result you are assessing) and use the judgement for all the previous domains as a basis for the overall risk-of-bias judgement.

Context of risk of bias assessment

There are also two other important issues to consider when assessing a trial: conflicts of interests and bias due to missing evidence. Although they are not directly addressed in RoB 2, we will briefly present them in this section to provide context.

Industry funding and investigators' conflicts of interest

Industry funding of medical research and financial relationships between researchers and sponsors are considered a concern for the external and internal validity of randomised trials.^{9,10}

A group of researchers of the Cochrane Bias Methods Group is currently developing a Tool for Addressing Conflicts of Interest in Trials, named TACIT.¹¹ The aim of TACIT is to assess in a trial whether there is reason for notable concern due to conflicts of interest. Conflicts of interests may impact on the risk of bias in a trial (which is addressed by the domains in RoB2), on the risk for non-publication bias (see below) and on the external validity of the trial (which we do not directly address in this context). TACIT is not yet finalised but some of its elements will be incorporated in the assessment of the trials included in the living network meta-analysis. You will be required to:

1. **Check whether funding source is disclosed.** You usually find this information at the bottom of the article. Please note who funded the study and any involvement of funder employees or external commercial parties hired by the funder (e.g., a medical writer). Presence of employees of drug/device manufacturers among the co-authors will be considered a form of study funding.
2. **Categorize the funding source** as follows:
 - a. Private (this will include any type of private sector stakeholders: e.g., pharmaceutical/device companies, insurance companies)
 - b. Public/non profit
 - c. Mixed (this will include: a) trials funded by both categories 1 and 2 above, b) trials funded by the public sector where the drug/devices were donated by a drug/device company)

⁹Ahn R, Woodbridge A, Abraham A, et al. Financial ties of principal investigators and randomized controlled trial outcomes: cross sectional study. *BMJ* 2017;356:i6770.

¹⁰Lundh A, Lexchin J, Mintzes B, Schroll JB, Bero L. Industry sponsorship and research outcome. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews*. 2017;2:Mr000033.

¹¹Lundh A, Boutron I, Stewart L, Hróbjartsson A. What to do with a clinical trial with conflicts of interest. *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine* 2020;25:157-158.

- d. No specific funding (when the authors state that no specific funding was received for the study)
 - e. Not reported/unclear
3. **Check whether the investigators' conflict of interest is disclosed.** You will consider conflict of interest only of the primary investigators (typically first and last author of main trial publication and any trial statisticians, if identifiable).
 4. **Categorize the conflicts of interest as:**
 - a. There are conflicts of interest
 - b. There are no conflicts of interest
 - c. Lack of conflict of interest disclosure

Risk of bias due to missing evidence

For any subsequent meta-analysis of the included trials, another important issue to consider is the risk of bias due to missing results.

RoB 2 assesses risk of bias in available study results (bias in selection of the reported result) and does not address selective non-reporting of results. A new tool named ROB-ME¹² is currently being developed to assess risk of bias due to unavailable studies (publication bias) and unavailable study results (selective reporting bias).

For the purpose of this project, you will be required to assess which of the outcomes of the living network meta-analysis are reported and which are not reported in each COVID-19 trial based on the pre-specified outcomes listed in the trial protocol or registry. In order to do that, for each COVID-19 trial you will compare the outcomes between registry/protocol and final report. If at least one pre-specified outcome is unreported, you will add a comment in the 'Overall comment' section for each trial using a statement like the following: '*Some outcomes pre-specified in the registry (e.g., time to clinical improvement) were not reported in the article*'.

For outcomes not included in the protocol of the living network meta-analysis,¹³ you will not be required to conduct this assessment.

¹²Page MJ, Sterne JAC, Boutron I, et al. Risk Of Bias due to Missing Evidence (ROB-ME) : a new tool for assessing risk of non-reporting biases in evidence syntheses. Available at : <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BaF3lZ6j1ZlX208gsoYab8uGzk6z1qvw/view>.

¹³Boutron I, Chaimni A, Devane D, et al. Interventions for preventing and treating COVID-19: protocol for a living mapping of research and a living systematic review. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3820266#.Xs432Mj7Q2w>.

PART 3. KEY RESOURCES

<https://www.riskofbias.info/welcome/rob-2-0-tool>

This website provides detailed guidance on the RoB2 tool and gives you access to:

- the full guidance document;
- the cribsheet which summarises the tool, signalling questions and key considerations for reaching risk of bias judgements;
- a template for completing the assessment;
- an Excel tool to implement RoB 2.

Training videos on RoB 2 are available at the following [link](#). The RoB 2 Learning Live webinar series provides ten videos that guide you through each step of assessing risk of bias using RoB 2.